

A Review on Human Consciousness Toward Sustainable Fashion Behaviour

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Abstract:

Fast fashion and fast disposal are the trends that have been following the past few years. Adapting to this has pushed the human consciousness to a lower level that people don't think about the impact a task will cause but rather just see the satisfaction that they get after the act. This article is about the lifecycle of clothing, from the state of pre-consumer and post-consumer lifecycle of textiles. This has been an unnoticed context because people just buy, use and dispose but they are unaware of all impacts that they are causing to the environment, such impacts have their effects on various forms of life in the surrounding. Therefore, this paper emphasizes using the 4R approaches like "REDUCE, REUSE, RECYCLE and RECOVER" to help with the solution for the impact caused by fashion minded people or the task of producing such fast fashion garments.

Keywords: *Carbon emission, environmental impact, fast fashion, sustainable, waste management*

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1. Introduction

The textile and apparel industry is the world's third-largest manufacturing sector after the automobile and technology industry. Its working model is intensifying the issue by leaping forward the rate of design and production. With the growing market and consumer's behavior to buy more clothes worldwide, the cheap items and new styles are taking a toll on the environment. Today, apparel production is the world's second most polluting industry next to the oil industry. The total carbon emissions from textile production in the current situation remain at 1.2 billion tons every year [1]. The sector's emissions are to spike more than 60% by 2030 if we don't foresee a change toward a sustainable fashion industry anytime soon [2]. The textiles industry proceeds in almost a procedural manner with the humongous quantity of non-renewable resources used to manufacture textile products and clothes, which are often used for only a short time; such highly esteemed clothing is dumped in landfills every year due to underutilisation and lack of recycling or reusing [3]. The replacement of clothing is no more a seasonal (spring summer/autumn winter) buying behaviour. It has become more frequent that people buy clothing every few weeks/months. Buyer's requirements can be fulfilled by the many cost-effective retail stores that offer new designs each week. In 2000, 50 billion new garments were made, and almost 20 years later, the figure multiplied [4]. In this increasing scenario, less than 5 % of used clothing is reused or recycled into new clothing and others ultimately end up in the landfill. It shows the resources used to derive such clothing have been wasted [5]. These factors combined make it a challenging task for the manufacturers to develop clothing without causing an impact on the environment, and to become eco-friendly and sustainable while additionally advancing better conditions for labourers in the unit. The industry's progress toward a sustainable model is increasing pace. Designers are exploring new aspects, to explore the region's biodiversity in promoting sustainable brands [6]. The process by which we design, produce, and the usage of clothing has drawbacks that are becoming increasingly transparent. The sustainable approach is required and holds even more importance as this is the year of the pandemic. One thing that we can follow is to understand and act according to the limits to which humans can push nature before it can negatively affect us in return [7]. Sustainable manufacturing and usage of clothing are all about doing great and better with less environmental impact [8]. This can have an impact on the aspects of life in matters of environmental degradation, increasing resource restoration, and promoting sustainable lifestyles in the minds of people.

2. Methods

Literature reviews were carried out to analyse the consumer and manufacturing initiatives, along with technological developments that have been involved in the last 15 years to understand and control textile waste. The search area for this review article is based on textile products, product life cycle, consumer behaviour, waste management, recycling, sustainable approaches and 4R concepts. From the analysis there is a comprehensive approach and awareness have been initiated worldwide to control landfill waste and utilise the textile product efficiently.

3. Discussions

3.1. Lifecycle of Textile

Textile products inventiveness and novelties are presented based on the life cycle of textile products and figure 1 shows the same.

Figure 1 - Textile Product Life Cycle

3.1.1. Pre-consumer life of textile

The pre-consumer life of a textile includes different stages of production involved to come up with the desired garment, production of fibres on farms, making raw fibres into yarns and weaving yarns in the form of fabric, and eventually, the fabric into garment all processes come under pre-consumer life of textile. All these stages have individual process sequences to return up with the raw material for the subsequent process [9]. From the production of fibre or making the yarn or weaving/knitting them into fabrics and then cutting/sewing them into a garment, all these processes have an individual impact on the environment when the resource usage limit is not maintained. The variants in waste percentage can be varied depending on the multiple factors for instance, defective processes, faulty designs and extra materials bought to meet customer's minimums, but on average, the product process and samples account for the utmost whole waste generation [10]. Especially in the apparel manufacturing process, the cutting department sums up the maximum leftovers and the finishing department is the least. According to a study done by [11] in t-shirt manufacturing, the utmost wastage is from the cutting department, being in an average of 13.57%, in the control panel at 6.91%, in sewing at 4.31% and in finishing at 1.72%, with a total around of 26.51% wastages of the original fabric. Apart from the process waste, the wastage starts from the cultivation of raw materials like fibres, which requires the consumption of resources in the form of water, heat & electricity, labor, etc., are required to finish the cycle of production.

3.1.1.1. Environmental Impacts

The production has increased to almost 20% in 2019 due to the fast fashion market, which requires tons of resources than the usual limit to keep the fast fashion market going. Therefore, the consumption made by fast fashion regarding water, fossils for heat and electricity, and labour has made an impact [12]. The utilised resources like water used for printing/dyeing/washing which accounts for 17% to 20% of water pollution are not disposed of properly and are left untreated. It ends up in the water streams causing an impact on humans and aquatic life which needs the water stream. The possible approach to this impact is to reduce the production of fast fashion garments but instead to make good quality products with longevity and reusing the products will reduce the resource depletion.

This take-make-dispose kind of product reflects impacts on the environment, which in return makes it a hard time for any life that exists on earth. These harmful substances influence and degrade the quality of health for textile workers and consumers who use those clothes, and this substance escapes into the environment.

The carbon emission caused by every action that a human does causes an impact in protecting the environment from causing any harm to humans in from production of any natural fibre or making any synthetic fibre it releases Greenhouse gases (GHGs) in the surrounding and later each process like cleaning and washing fibres, running machines to produce yarns and fabrics also emit GHG [13]. Instead of producing small lifecycle garments, making garments with the fibres procured from existing/end-of-life textile waste from mills can reduce the amount of carbon emitted [14] and also reusing such products will reduce the process of the derived product from virgin materials. These are a few influences caused by the textile and apparel industry to environmental growth associated with pre-consumer lifecycle of textiles.

3.1.1.2. Waste Management or Disposal

Fibre stage cotton when sent to the production of yarns is initially opened and cleaned and then a series of the process happens before the fibre is converted into a fabric [15] and in course of these stages long and some short staples will be in the process but all those too short fibres will be in the air and this is known as cotton dust. This kind of too short fibre/cotton dust cannot be used in any textile application and this kind of waste is mostly burnt to dispose of which in return causes carbon emission [16]. Therefore, having suctioned or exhaust fans to collect this cotton dust and sustainably dispose of it by recovering energy in the means of biogas production, vermin-composting and fuel for the boiler.

In the fabric stage, wastage can occur concerning the defects that are caused in the fabric during the weaving or knitting process, and these defective fabrics will not be approved or accepted by the manufacturers or buyers for the order. In such cases, either the defective fabric can be reused by upcycling it in any other form or by recycling it to obtain another raw material that can be made into a new product [17].

In the production process initially, various samples will be sent here and there for the buyer's approval and these samples will end up in waste. Then, during the process of printing/dyeing process, several strikes off samples and defective pieces will be obtained which is ultimately a waste component. In bulk production, the fabric is laid into the ply and then the cutting happens, here the cutting waste is obtained [18]. Reusing these waste elements in the form of upcycling them into a new product that can be used in home textiles or any other textile application rather than ending up in landfills or burnt [19].

The majority of pre-consumer textile waste of these kinds is collected as municipal solid waste (MSW) and is burnt with the energy recovery concept [20]. But rather these components of waste have not been used by consumers therefore, it is nearly a virgin material that can be reused in various applications such as upcycling goods, stuffing material in soft toys/ home textiles [21], or can be recycled into fibre state again to come up with the garment rather than directly putting up as a recovering energy source. Starting the new production cycle and then the whole process continues which results in improper disposal of waste and unwanted usage of the resources for a new production which also causes carbon emissions [22, 23].

Recycling and efficiently reusing pre-consumer textile waste can cut down or reduce the production of new textiles and apparel from virgin materials and hence reduce the use of resources like water, energy and chemicals during the production chain [24]. In addition to that various risks associated with the chemicals used in the textile industry may be avoided by reducing the huge consumption of textiles in the first place [25], especially those which are made with unnecessarily huge chemicals just for the sake of trend-led fashion.

3.1.2. Post-consumer life of textile

The post-consumer life of textiles includes a different series of stages that follow after a customer purchases a garment in the retail store [26]. The usage, washing, drying, and wear and tear aspects of a garment play an important role when it comes to the durability of a garment and also due to the fast fashion trend the longevity of the garment collection has become too short than a few years back [27]. The fast fashion cycle in recent years is focused on a trend that leads to profit and cheap clothing, customers buy a garment and instead of a seasonal purchase now it has become a sub-seasonal purchase [28]. Because the retail stores make it a deadline to drop a new collection every week and customers are forced to make a purchase of the design in the fright of missing it out for the next time when they visit the store.

Purchasing a garment is not a big deal, it is a matter of money but when it comes to maintaining a garment and extending its permanence. It requires patience and resources to do the task [29]. This simply conveys the fact that resources like human effort, water, heat and electricity are needed to have a good ironed garment in our wardrobe. Again usage of all these resources more than a certain limit will be an impactful situation for the environment.

3.1.2.1. Environmental impacts

Fast fashion is a trend term used to sell bulk made goods at the lowest price and is focused only on economic growth in terms of profit but is not concerned about the influences these show on environmental growth [30]. Therefore, consumers need to know the sustainable approach toward environmental health and consciously avoid such fashion choices [31]. Instead of going with a big production number with less quality material for cheap prices, if the garments are made with good quality material that can last longer in a moderate price range will encourage people to buy and also when they want to dispose of these garments can be recycled or reused rather than burning or throwing them in landfills and then making new products again from scratch [32]. This approach can reduce the resources used in the process and save them for the future.

Reduction efforts for greenhouse gas emissions are known as accelerated abatement [33], with clothing brands and retail manufacturers as the main primary elements. A few such important aspects such as reducing the carbon emissions from the upstream process and the brand's self-oriented operations, and encouraging consumers to follow sustainable behaviours [34] were a few such attempts of this reduction process.

In the course of usage of a garment, washing several times and each time washed and dry, micro-fibres release into the water stream which is a big issue. When the usage of purchased clothes, several million tonnes of CO₂ are emitted every year [35] from the process of washing and drying clothes. It leads to carbon emissions and this was not a big deal a few years back but now it has become a huge number that will have a harmful impact on the environment [36]. Therefore, reducing production and reusing/recycling the existing products can be a good solution to this issue.

3.1.2.2. Waste management or disposal

The naturally occurring fibres will demand higher energy for the decomposition process when compared with synthetic fibres, also synthetic fibres release microfibrils into the water which can eventually end up in oceans. Such microfibrils realised from natural materials break down quicker than synthetic materials which take a very long time and can be eaten by sea animals. Therefore, just washing causes many issues and when such kind of garment is disposed of in the ocean or landfills it is a nightmare to imagine the impacts that these could cause in our day-to-day life. In this case, both the ocean and land are polluted with excessive production of garments [37].

These days people have a big wardrobe where a teen girl/boy has an average of 20-30 t-shirts and 6-8 denim/skirts with a variety of footwear to match the outfit [38], all this is not an essential thing but just to be aesthetically satisfied. From this, we can analyse that fast fashion has resulted in huge production numbers and all of these will be accumulated in landfills or will be burned to dispose of them, either way, it will cause an impact on the environment [39].

Fast fashion has forced our fashion population to buy more than needed and this ultimately is less durable clothing which is degraded in a few washes and then people throw away these and build their wardrobe with new collections and this cycle continues [40]. This has made landfills more crowded than ever before and being 3rd biggest country the waste treatment for such problem is still not having. A clear solution is adapting an approach like buying recycled clothing rather than new virgin clothing can save money and also resources required to make the recycled products are only half the new product [41]. Also when landfills are crowded and during the rainy season the synthetic fibres release microfibre into the water streams causing harm to both aquatic life and human life which depend on the water source and this donates the effect of ocean plastic pollution [42].

The most preferred option to get rid of this excess clothing or waste clothing is by burning them to recover energy which again contributes to carbon emissions and is a very big cause of the climatic disasters that have occurred in recent years and then manufacturers make a completely new product from the virgin materials which is a source to resource waste and time waste [43]. Instead of all these aspects, a sustainable alternate option would be to recycle or reuse garments rather than buying new garments, in this recent analysis it is found that

only 5-8% of clothing is being recycled and all others are dumped in landfills which are ultimately burned [44]. Therefore, following a good alternative measure to burning these garments would be the best option and the customers or manufacturers can understand the importance of recycling and the rate is expected to rise with such awareness.

3.2. 4R Concepts:

The makers or buyers in the form of customers, buyers, manufacturers, retailers and disposers are required to overcome these issues caused by adapting the fast fashion model which was not an aesthetic behaviour but rather a functional behavior. The consumers who are fashion minded with no concern about the impacts that would cause to the environment in the upcoming future. Rather than scaling up production and increasing profits fashion brands, and manufacturers can adopt sustainable approaches to produce a garment in the required quantity to make the best out of existing products by adapting the concept of 4R has been encouraged and enhanced.

The 4R concept denotes the sustainable approach for the betterment of the environment and also the human quality of life in such surroundings will be enriched. The benefit of each R in the 4R is explained in the context: of **“REDUCE”** this aspect suggests the consumers and also the manufacturers focus on both quality and quantity on an equal basis and not just on quantity [45]. If the quality is to be the main focus then the commitment required to make a garment would be more than that of quantity focused garments, and in quantity focused garments all that matters is a huge production and this would just exhaust the resources given rise to water scarcity and other resources like heat and electricity produced by fossil a scarcity and this results in carbon emission which is again a regrettable reality [46]. To bring the reduction of resources into the picture then **“REUSE”** products that are in the urge of being thrown away for disposal [47]. Reusing is nothing but to up-cycle an existing product into a better product so that people would prefer to buy them for their added aesthetic or functional quality and make the best out of them rather than dumping those products in landfills or burning them for energy recovery [48]. Another alternate option to the reuse method is to donate products to non-charitable organisations or give them away to second-hand stores where they up-cycle these and develop them aesthetically for the second purchase and the life of such products is increased rather than buying a virgin product [49]. Even then if the fact of those products being already used exists in the minds of people, such products can be made into a new product with the concept of **“RECYCLE”**, this helps a product to be utilised in a completely unique way because it is all the way made from the starting process except that the raw material comes from pre-existed product. These processes have a big impact on the development of the environment and help eradicate the landfills but only 5% of total clothing [50] is recycled and others end up in landfills/ oceans or sent for burning. Recently, several brands like H&M and ZARA have been approaching this recycling option to become sustainable brands and be eco-friendly [51]. Whereas few other brands have stated “if customers give them a garment for recycling they would get an offer of 10%” which is making new marketing strategies to make the consumer aware of the importance of recycling [52] rather than buying new virgin products made from complete virgin materials. Another main reason to take recycling of products forward is that making a product from recycled materials uses only 30-50% of a total resource than making a virgin product and carbon emission is reduced to up to 60% when a product is made from recycled materials. Because the most carbon emission is found to happen due to the fibre production stage in the farms [53]. The last no other choice option is to **“RECOVER”** when the material cannot be reused or recycled from an existing product due to several reasons, and this process can help in recovering the energy spent to make the product and can be refurbished in any other process so the no new energy is exhausted [54]. All these are the segmentation of 4R in the lifecycle of a product and making the best use of a product at every stage can save resources needed to make new products from scratch and eradicate the fast fashion concept where only profit is the main focus and not the environment.

4. Conclusion

The fashion industry is responsible for a major part of textile production. People nowadays buy 60% more clothing due to fast fashion trends than what they used to buy 20 years ago. This has caused environmental impacts that are now reflected as climatic disorders and environmental backfires. Also, the fashion industry is accountable for 15% of annual global carbon emissions. It exceeds any other industry by leaping the range of greenhouse gases emitted in various other fields. From all these matters we can undeniably state that the effects caused by the fashion industry will spike the levels of carbon footprint in the near future. Therefore, People should start adapting to buying clothes which is a necessity and avoid unwanted purchases each time they visit malls or each time they see a new collection. Instead of people or customers thinking for a moment and then reacting they can understand if that purchase is really needed for them. Maintaining a limit on resource

consumption can result in well balanced state, or else nature would backfire on the surroundings which will be hard for the human race to face reality. Therefore, adapting the 4R approaches like “REDUCE, REUSE, RECYCLE and RECOVER” can help people understand the importance of a sustainable and eco-friendly environment. Understanding the ways to manage/dispose of waste and understanding the impacts caused by underused/ overused clothing can help us move to a better lifestyle with better environmental surroundings. Hence, human consciousness in the form of customers, buyers, manufacturers, retailers and disposers is required to overcome these issues which have arisen knowingly or unknowingly by the fast fashion industry and the consumers who are fashion minded with no concern about the impacts that would cause to the environment in upcoming future.

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